

TEACHER AND STUDENT VIEWS ON THE CAUSES OF ORAL PRESENTATION ANXIETY AND HOW TO REDUCE IT IN TURKISH LANGUAGE CLASSES¹

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Abstract

This study aims to identify, based on students' and teachers' perspectives, the sources of anxiety that occur during oral expression activities in Turkish lessons, as well as the strategies used to reduce this anxiety. The study group includes 18 students attending a public middle school during the 2025-2026 academic year and 14 Turkish language teachers working in four different middle schools. The research employed a case study design, which is a qualitative research method. Data were collected through a semi-structured interview form and analyzed using content analysis. According to students, the primary sources of oral expression anxiety are public speaking, unexpected questions, fear of making mistakes, using the smartboard, and peer reactions. Lack of self-confidence, being unprepared, teacher attitude, and classroom atmosphere are significant factors that heighten anxiety. To alleviate anxiety, students use strategies such as rehearsing, note-taking, breathing exercises, peer support, and focusing techniques. Teachers view anxiety as multidimensional, with public speaking being the most common. Factors like lack of self-confidence, preparation level, peer pressure, and classroom climate influence anxiety levels. Teachers highlight that one-on-one support, reassuring communication, confidence-building activities, gradual presentation opportunities, and a positive classroom environment effectively reduce anxiety.

ORTAOKUL ÖĞRENCİLERİNİN SÖZLÜ ANLATIM KAYGILARININ KAYNAKLARINA VE AZALTILMASINA YÖNELİK ÖĞRETMEN VE ÖĞRENCİ GÖRÜŞLERİ

Makale Bilgisi

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Özet

Bu araştırmanın amacı, Türkçe derslerinde sözlü anlatım etkinlikleri sırasında ortaya çıkan kaygının kaynaklarını ve bu kaygıyı azaltmaya yönelik stratejileri öğrencilerin ve öğretmenlerin görüşleri doğrultusunda belirlemektir. Çalışma grubunu, 2025-2026 eğitim öğretim yılında bir devlet ortaokulunda öğrenim gören 18 öğrenci ile dört farklı ortaokulda görev yapan 14 Türkçe öğretmeni oluşturmaktadır. Araştırma, nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden durum çalışması deseniyle yürütülmüştür. Veriler yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formu aracılığıyla toplanmış ve içerik analiziyle çözümlenmiştir. Öğrenci görüşlerine göre sözlü anlatım kaygısının temel kaynakları topluluk önünde konuşma, hazırlıksız sorular, yanlış yapma korkusu, akıllı tahta kullanımı ve akran tepkileridir. Öz güven eksikliği, hazırlıksızlık, öğretmen tutumu ve sınıf atmosferi kaygıyı artıran önemli etkenlerdir. Öğrenciler kaygıyı azaltmak için prova yapma, not kullanma, nefes egzersizleri, arkadaş desteği ve dikkat toplama gibi stratejilerden yararlanmaktadır. Öğretmen görüşleri, kaygının çok boyutlu olduğunu göstermektedir. Öğretmenlere göre topluluk önünde konuşma kaygısı en yaygın türdür. Öz güven eksikliği, hazırlık düzeyi, akran baskısı ve sınıf atmosferi belirleyici faktörlerdir. Öğretmenler birebir destek, rahatlatıcı iletişim, öz güven geliştirici etkinlikler, kademeli sunum fırsatları ve olumlu sınıf ikliminin kaygıyı azaltmada etkili olduğunu vurgulamışlardır.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Language is the most basic tool for communication, allowing individuals to express their emotions, thoughts, and experiences. As a key means of passing down cultural heritage from generation to generation, language is a living structure that influences both how people think and how they communicate (Baki & Karakuş, 2015). Halliday (1978) sees language as a system for producing and sharing meaning, realizing the potential of social culture. Özbay (2012), on the other hand, views language as a complete structure comprising listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. Among these, speaking is critical because it enables individuals to express themselves and actively engage in social life.

Although speaking skills naturally develop at a young age, many people face emotional barriers when speaking in person, especially in educational settings (Boylu & Çangal, 2015). The most common of these barriers is speech anxiety. The Turkish Language Institution (2025) defines anxiety as “a disturbing emotion arising from the fear that something bad or distressing will happen; concern, worry, apprehension, distress,” while Scovel (1991) describes anxiety as the discomfort and tension a person feels when facing perceived threats. In educational contexts, speech anxiety refers to the physical, emotional, and mental tension individuals experience when speaking in front of a group, giving a presentation, or participating in oral activities (Demir & Melanlıoğlu, 2014). This condition can manifest as symptoms such as heart palpitations, sweating, tremor of the voice, headaches, forgetfulness, and confusion (Demir & Melanlıoğlu, 2014; Türkçapar, 2004).

The causes of speech anxiety are linked to personal, environmental, and educational factors. On a personal level, lack of self-confidence, inadequate preparation, and negative self-view are common. In contrast, at the environmental level, teacher attitudes, peer responses, and evaluation pressure play significant roles (Kardaş, 2015). Indeed, as middle-school students grow more sensitive to social evaluation during adolescence, oral activities in the classroom can lead to intense anxiety.

Speech anxiety is not only an emotional problem but also a matter of self-efficacy that directly affects the learning process. According to Bandura’s (1997) theory of self-efficacy, an individual’s belief in their ability to successfully perform a task is the strongest psychological variable determining their performance. Students with high self-efficacy continue to make efforts even in challenging tasks, whereas those with low self-efficacy tend to avoid tasks due to expectations of failure (Pajares & Schunk, 2001). Studies by Arslan (2018) and Arslan et al. (2019) show that as students’ academic self-efficacy levels increase, their speech anxiety significantly decreases. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2020) report that students’ self-efficacy levels directly contribute to their speaking performance.

In Turkey, numerous studies have examined speech anxiety (Sallabaş, 2012; Kavruk & Deniz, 2015; Şen & Boylu, 2015; Arslan, 2018; Akalın & Adıgüzel, 2020; Aydın & Kayman, 2021; Keşaplı & Çifci, 2024). In addition, in the literature, there are various studies evaluating middle-school students’ speaking skills from the perspectives of teachers (Demir & Gül-Özdil, 2019), examining the effect of prepared speech on reducing the speech anxiety of Turkish language teacher candidates (Özdemir, 2018), investigating speech anxiety levels of classroom teaching students (Kuru, 2018), analyzing the impact of practices in oral expression courses on the speech anxiety of teacher candidates (Kuşdemir & Katrancı, 2015), and evaluating middle-school students’ English speaking anxiety based on teacher and student views (Özcanlı & Kozikoğlu, 2023). However, studies that examine the speech anxiety experienced by students specifically in Turkish lessons based on both their own views and experiences as well as the evaluations of teachers who witness this process are limited. However, oral expression skills are critical for enabling students to structure their thoughts, convey emotions, and participate actively in social interactions.

Accordingly, this study, aiming to fill the identified gap in the existing literature, systematically reveals — through student and teacher perspectives — the primary sources of oral expression anxiety experienced by middle-school students in Turkish lessons and develops student-centered and teacher-supported solution proposals to reduce this anxiety. It is expected that the study's findings will contribute at both the academic and practical levels to the design of instructional processes and the development of educational policies.

The purpose of this study is to identify the reasons for anxiety among middle school students during oral expression activities in Turkish lessons and to evaluate solutions to reduce this anxiety from the perspectives of students and Turkish language teachers. Within this scope, answers were sought for the following research questions:

1. During oral expression activities in Turkish lessons, in what situations do students experience anxiety, and how do teachers evaluate the situations in which this anxiety mostly occurs?
2. What personal and environmental factors contribute to students' oral expression anxiety, and how do teachers interpret these factors?
3. What strategies do students use to reduce their oral expression anxiety, and what methods and practices do teachers implement to help lessen this anxiety?
4. How do students describe an oral expression environment in which they feel more comfortable expressing themselves, and according to teachers, what characteristics define a classroom environment that helps students speak more confidently?
5. What solutions do students suggest to reduce oral expression anxiety, and based on teacher evaluations, which practices are most effective in alleviating this anxiety?

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Model

This research utilized a case study design, a qualitative research method. A case study is a qualitative research approach that aims to explore a specific phenomenon in depth within its real-life context (Yin, 2018). This method allows the researcher to seek comprehensive answers to the questions of “what,” “how,” and “why.” The phenomenon studied is the oral expression anxiety experienced by students in Turkish lessons. The context includes middle school learning environments where this anxiety occurs and teachers' in-class practices for managing it. Both the causes of anxiety, based on students' experiences, and teachers' observations and evaluations were addressed holistically. The research aims to provide a detailed description of the phenomenon, understand how anxiety manifests, and propose solutions from both student and teacher perspectives. The case study design was considered suitable for this purpose, as it reveals the relationship between the phenomenon and individual as well as environmental factors (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Merriam, 2009). Within this framework, the anxiety students experience during oral expression was examined thoroughly through participant interviews and open-ended questions conducted in their natural environment. Additionally, teachers' opinions, classroom observations, practices, and evaluations regarding anxiety were gathered. This approach allowed participants to share their experiences from their own perspectives, enabling a multidimensional analysis of the phenomenon.

2.1. Study Group

This research was conducted during the first semester of the 2025–2026 academic year with fifth-, sixth-, seventh-, and eighth-grade students at a public middle school in Van province. The study group consists of 18 students who voluntarily agreed to participate. The group included 10 females and 8 males, and including students from different grade levels allowed for observing changes in oral expression anxiety across grades. Additionally, the study involved 14 Turkish language teachers from four middle schools in the same province. Eight of the teachers were women, and six were men. Including teachers alongside students enabled the examination of oral

expression anxiety from multiple perspectives, including students' experiences and teachers' observations.

2.2. Data Collection Tool

The data were gathered using a semi-structured interview form developed by the researchers. When preparing the interview form, studies on speech anxiety and self-efficacy were reviewed. In line with the research's purpose, an initial pool of potential questions related to the topic was created. This question pool was then reviewed by two expert Turkish language teachers and two faculty members from the Department of Turkish Education. After considering their feedback, the form was revised and finalized. In its final version, the interview form includes five open-ended questions aligned with the research questions. These questions aim to explore students' levels of oral expression anxiety, the situations that trigger it, and coping strategies. The semi-structured format allows students to express their thoughts freely, while also enabling the researcher to request clarification through guiding questions if needed. Since teacher perspectives are also part of the research, a separate semi-structured interview form was developed for teachers. This teacher form also contains five open-ended questions, designed to comprehensively evaluate the development of students' oral expression anxiety through teacher observations and classroom practices.

2.3. Data Collection Process

Interviews were conducted after obtaining written consent from the students. Within the scope of the research, a quiet environment was provided at the school, where students could focus without distractions and complete the form comfortably. Each student individually filled out the semi-structured interview form. Although the time to complete the form varied among students, it averaged 25 minutes.

The researchers remained present throughout the process to ensure that students understood the questions correctly and received necessary explanations. After completing the forms, responses were carefully collected and prepared for analysis. This method allowed students to express their thoughts in their own words and ensured reliable data collection.

The data collection process for teachers was conducted similarly. Necessary permissions were obtained from the school administration and teachers for teacher interviews, and a quiet, suitable environment was arranged in accordance with the teachers' schedules. Teachers completed the semi-structured interview form individually. The average completion time ranged from 20 to 30 minutes. Throughout the process, the researchers provided clarification to teachers when questions needed explanation. Responses from the teacher forms were also collected carefully and included in the analysis. This approach enabled teachers to express their observations and experiences in detail and facilitated the collection of multidimensional data.

2.4. Data Analysis

The data from the research were analyzed using content analysis, a widely used qualitative research method. Using this method, responses from teachers and students to the semi-structured interview forms were carefully examined and organized into meaningful units. Teacher and student expressions were coded as basic units of meaning, similar codes conveying common content and meaning were grouped and transformed into categories, and finally into broader themes. To increase data reliability, the coding process was conducted independently by two researchers. The participant teachers were coded as TÖ1, TÖ2, TÖ3, while students were coded as Ö1, Ö2, Ö3, etc., to ensure anonymity and systematic data tracking. Inter-coder reliability was calculated using the formula proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994), yielding an average consistency of 89%. This high agreement rate supports the reliability of the analysis process and the consistency of the findings. The findings were presented both in tables and supported with direct quotations from teacher and student statements. This approach ensured that the findings were explained with concrete examples, enabling readers to understand the experiences of teachers and students better.

3. FINDINGS

In this section, the opinions of teachers and students regarding oral presentation anxiety are presented in tables organized by themes, codes, and categories.

3.1. Findings Obtained from Teacher Opinions

Table 1. Teacher Opinions on Situations in Which Students Experience Anxiety During Oral Expression Activities

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Anxiety Situations	Public speaking	Anxiety of speaking in a crowded classroom environment	6	25,00
		Inability to maintain speech when going to the board	3	12,50
	Question-answer process	Anxiety of being caught unprepared for sudden questions	5	20,84
		Anxiety of making mistakes in questions where the teacher expects a specific answer	2	8,33
	Performance anxiety	Fear of saying something wrong/appearing ridiculous	3	12,50
		Anxiety of being unprepared/not having studied enough	2	8,33
	Peer relations	Anxiety of being mocked/belittled by friends	3	12,50

Table 1 shows the types of anxiety students experience during oral expression in Turkish lessons based on teacher evaluations. In the analysis, a total of 24 opinions were coded, as some teachers reported more than one situation of anxiety. The findings indicate that public speaking anxiety is the most common. Six teachers (25.00%) reported anxiety about speaking in a crowded classroom, while three teachers (12.50%) noted anxiety about losing their train of thought when going to the board. In the question-and-answer phase, five opinions (20.84%) expressed anxiety about being caught unprepared for sudden questions, and two opinions (8.33%) described anxiety about making mistakes on questions where the teacher expects a specific answer. Concerning performance anxiety, the fear of saying something wrong or appearing ridiculous appeared in three opinions (12.50%), and anxiety from being unprepared or not having studied enough was mentioned in two opinions (8.33%). In the peer relations category, the anxiety of being mocked or belittled by friends was reported in three opinions (12.50%). Following the general distribution from Table 1 and the above explanations, some opinions are presented below as direct quotes to better illustrate teachers' observations and evaluations regarding students' oral expression anxiety.

"In general, they experience anxiety about appearing in front of an audience." (TÖ6).

"When they go to the board, most students forget what to say and become anxious." (TÖ2).

"When sudden questions are asked, there is a noticeable anxiety in students." (TÖ4).

"They become excited and experience serious anxiety before speaking in response to questions that require a certain answer." (TÖ3).

"They experience anxiety due to the fear of saying something wrong." (TÖ5).

"Students experience anxiety when the classroom environment is tense or when they are not adequately prepared." (TÖ12).

"They feel anxious while speaking because they fear being belittled in front of their friends." (TÖ13).

Table 2. Teacher Opinions on Personal and Environmental Factors Effective in the Emergence of Oral Expression Anxiety in Students

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Personal and Environmental Factors	Self-confidence	Lack of self-confidence	10	35,71
	Peer relations	Peer pressure/anxiety of being criticized	7	25,00
	Classroom atmosphere	Tense classroom environment/teacher attitude	5	17,86
	Preparation level	Lack of preparation before the lesson	4	14,29
	Personal traits	Anxiety caused by personal temperament	2	7,14

Table 2 shows the personal and environmental factors linked to the development of oral expression anxiety among students, based on teachers' reports. A total of 28 opinions were collected. This reflects how teachers focus on multiple factors at once. Among personal factors, lack of self-confidence is the most common, with 10 opinions (35.71%). Students' levels of preparation were noted in four opinions (14.29%), and personal traits or temperament were mentioned twice (7.14%) as other personal influences on anxiety. For environmental factors, peer pressure and fear of criticism were cited in seven opinions (25.00%). In comparison, classroom atmosphere and teacher attitude were mentioned in five opinions (17.86%) as additional factors that increase anxiety. Following the numerical data in Table 2, teachers' observations and assessments regarding the personal and environmental causes of oral expression anxiety are provided below as direct quotes.

"First of all, I think there are many reasons for this. After a negative experience, self-confidence problems may occur." (TÖ8).

"Students with a low level of preparation experience more anxiety during oral expression." (TÖ13).

"In some students, anxiety stems entirely from their personal temperament. Their shy or introverted nature makes it difficult for them to express themselves during oral expression." (TÖ2).

"The fear of being criticized by peers, and the classroom climate being suitable for this, increases anxiety." (TÖ14).

"A tense atmosphere and a strict teacher attitude directly affect students' anxiety levels." (TÖ12).

Table 3. Strategies Used by Teachers to Reduce Students' Oral Expression Anxiety

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Strategies Used to Reduce Anxiety	One-to-one support	Providing individual support to the student	5	22,72
	Comforting communication	Creating a calming communication style	4	18,18
	Confidence-building activities	Practices aimed at increasing self-confidence	4	18,18
	Informative preparation	Informing students before the activity	3	13,64
	Gradual application	Transitioning from individual practice to group work	3	13,64
	Positive classroom atmosphere	Establishing a favorable class climate	3	13,64

Table 3 shows the strategies teachers use to reduce students' oral expression anxiety. From the analysis, 22 responses were collected, as many teachers highlighted more than one strategy at a time. Providing individual support to students (22.72%), creating a comforting communication style (18.18%), and implementing confidence-building activities (18.18%) are the most common strategies used by teachers. These results suggest that strengthening students personally is crucial for reducing anxiety. Informing students before activities (13.64%), using gradual implementation (13.64%), and creating a positive classroom environment (13.64%) were also seen as important by teachers. These strategies highlight the need to build a classroom atmosphere that reduces triggers of anxiety. To better illustrate the strategies used by teachers, direct quotes from teachers' statements related to each category are included below.

Before the student begins oral expression, I stand beside them and accompany them. This physical and emotional support makes them feel safe. (TÖ1).

"I have a short joke or a motivational talk with them. This visibly reduces the student's tension." (TÖ7).

"I frequently include confidence-building activities. Emphasizing the student's strengths is very effective in reducing anxiety." (TÖ6).

"Before the oral activity, I explain the purpose of the activity and, in detail, what awaits them during the process. In this way, students do not experience anxiety caused by uncertainty." (TÖ3).

"First, I let them rehearse in an empty classroom, then we move on to small groups. Gradual increase reduces anxiety in a controlled way." (TÖ9).

"Instead of a strict and rigid attitude, I adopt a gentle and encouraging approach. A cheerful classroom environment significantly reduces anxiety." (TÖ11).

Table 4. Teachers' views on the oral expression environment where students can express themselves comfortably and freely

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Learning Environments that Reduce Anxiety	Supportive teacher attitude	The teacher demonstrates a warm, encouraging, and guiding approach.	8	30,77
	Trust-based atmosphere	The classroom atmosphere is sincere, reassuring, and free from judgment	6	23,08
	Attentive listener behavior	Participants exhibit respectful, understanding, and non-critical listening	4	15,38
	Student-centered activities	Activities are based on voluntariness and take place in a simple, distraction-free environment	4	15,38
	Focused listening environment	The audience maintains attention and provides constructive engagement	3	11,54
	Use of technology	Technological tools are employed effectively	1	3,85

Table 4 shows teachers' views on the qualities of oral expression environments that help students speak more comfortably and freely. The analysis identified 26 coded statements, as some teachers highlighted multiple attributes. The results reveal that teachers mainly value a supportive teacher attitude (30.77%) and a trust-based classroom climate (23.08%) for reducing students' anxiety. Additionally, respectful and attentive listener behavior (15.38%), student-centered activities (15.38%), an attentive listening environment (11.54%), and the effective use of technological tools (3.85%) are identified as other key factors that help lower anxiety levels.

Below are teachers' assessments of the features of an environment that allows students to express themselves more comfortably and freely during oral activities.

"A warm and encouraging teacher stance is considered essential for helping students articulate their ideas with ease." (TÖ10)

"A sincere yet balanced classroom atmosphere is viewed as supporting students' ability to speak without feeling pressured." (TÖ4)

"Raising awareness among listeners is regarded as a key element; when students know they will not face ridicule or harsh criticism, their confidence increases." (TÖ1)

"Activities that are voluntary and designed with students' prior knowledge in mind are seen as making oral expression more natural and less anxiety-provoking." (TÖ7)

"Creating an environment where attentive listening is prioritized is believed to both relax the speaker and enhance the effectiveness of the activity." (TÖ11)

"The effective integration of technological tools is also perceived as contributing to students' sense of self-confidence." (TÖ5)

Table 5. Teacher Opinions on Effective Methods and Practices for Reducing Students' Oral Expression Anxiety

Theme Category	Code	N	%	
Anxiety-Reducing Instructional Strategies	Step-by-step progress	Gradually involve the student in the process by starting with topics they are familiar with	6	16,67
	Improving oral communication skills	Including practices such as drama, projects, educational games and group work	6	16,67
	Reinforcement and support	Rewarding students, providing feedback, and motivating them	5	13,89
	Teacher guidance	Guiding with additions, corrections, or examples during the presentation	5	13,89
	Exposure and repetition	Exposing students to speaking to various audiences in a gradual manner	4	11,11
	Confidence-building activities	Focusing on self-confidence-building practices and motivation	4	11,11
	Distraction techniques	Diverting students' attention to different areas to reduce anxiety	3	8,33
	Exam-free and individual practice	Practice in one-on-one or small group settings without the pressure of an exam	3	8,33

Table 5 presents the methods and practices that teachers find effective for reducing students' oral presentation anxiety. A total of 36 opinions were coded from the analysis. Some teachers highlighted more than one method. The results show that teachers prioritize small-step progress and gradual process management (16.67%) and practices focused on improving oral presentation skills (16.67%). This is followed by reinforcement and support (13.89%), teacher guidance (13.89%), exposure and repetition activities (11.11%), and activities to build self-

confidence (11.11%). Distraction techniques (8.33%) and non-test, individualized strategies (8.33%) also emerge as effective approaches for easing anxiety. Below are teachers' assessments of methods and practices to reduce students' oral presentation anxiety.

"Gradually involving students in the process, starting with topics they have mastered, and expanding the explanation with questions are effective in reducing anxiety." (TÖ14).

"Positive feedback and encouraging words are effective in reducing anxiety." (TÖ5).

"I make additions or corrections as needed during the student's presentation. I redirect the student's attention away from anxious thoughts by asking them to provide examples." (TÖ3).

"I try to redirect the student's attention to different areas to prevent them from becoming overwhelmed." (TÖ4).

"Involving students in group activities through activities such as drama, projects, and educational games reduces anxiety." (TÖ9).

"Familiarizing students with different audiences through exposure techniques reduces anxiety." (TÖ6).

"I involve students in activities that boost their self-confidence. This helps them feel more comfortable during oral presentations." (TÖ11).

"Individual sessions without the pressure of exams make it easier for students to express themselves." (TÖ13).

3.2. Findings Obtained from Student Opinions

Table 6. Student Opinions on Situations in Which They Experience Anxiety During Oral Expression

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Anxiety Situations	Public speaking	Fear of giving a presentation	12	30,00
	Sudden questions	Fear of being questioned by a teacher	9	22,50
	Performance anxiety	Fear of making mistakes	7	17,50
	Smartboard use	Fear of sharing information	6	15,00
	Peer relations	Fear of being made fun of	6	15,00

Table 6 displays the most common types of anxiety students face during oral presentations in Turkish language classes. A total of 40 responses were collected for this analysis, and students reported experiencing more than one type of anxiety. The distribution shows that 12 participants (30.00%) mentioned public speaking anxiety, 9 participants (22.50%) mentioned answering teacher questions, 7 participants (17.50%) mentioned fear of making mistakes, 6 participants (15.00%) mentioned anxiety while using a smartboard, and 6 participants (15.00%) mentioned anxiety related to peer relationships.

In this context, to better understand the anxieties students face during oral presentations, some participants' opinions are shared below with direct quotes.

"When I speak in front of a group, I forget my words and get nervous. Sometimes my hands and feet shake when I speak. My voice gets hoarse, and I don't know what to say. This stresses me out." (Ö17)

"When the teacher asks me a question, I have a hard time answering. I pause for a long time before answering, and when my classmates look at me, I feel even more embarrassed. That's why I sometimes hesitate to answer even though I understand the question." (Ö3)

"I am afraid the class will laugh if I say something wrong." (Ö8)

"When I present on the smart board, my hands shake, and I struggle to speak. Feeling everyone looking at me while presenting makes me very nervous." (Ö1)

"I worry I will be embarrassed if my classmates make fun of me. If I make a mistake while speaking in class, I expect everyone to laugh at me, so I usually prefer to remain silent." (Ö12)

Table 7. Student opinions on personal and environmental factors that influence the emergence of anxiety

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Personal and Environmental Factors Affecting Anxiety	Lack of self-confidence	Lack of self-confidence	10	29,41
	Lack of preparation	Lack of pre-lesson preparation	8	23,53
	Peer relationships	Ridicule and mockery	8	23,53
	Teacher	Harsh and critical attitude	6	17,65
	Classroom environment	Noisy and distracting environment	2	5,88

Table 7 displays the personal and environmental factors that affect students' oral expression anxiety. The analysis identified 34 opinions, with students citing multiple factors. When looking at the distribution of opinions, 10 students (29.41%) mentioned lack of self-confidence, 8 students (23.53%) cited lack of preparation before class, 8 students (23.53%) pointed to anxiety caused by peer relationships, 6 students (17.65%) referenced the teacher's harsh or critical attitude, and 2 students (5.88%) identified a noisy or distracting classroom environment as main causes of anxiety. In this context, to better understand the personal and environmental influences on students' oral expression anxiety, some participants' opinions are shared below with direct quotes.

"Because I have low self-confidence, I constantly worry when speaking in class. Sometimes I do not know what to say." (Ö15)

"If I have not prepared well enough for class, my anxiety increases. I am afraid I will say something wrong." (Ö6)

"When the teacher criticizes me, it is hard to express myself. I constantly think I will make mistakes." (Ö12)

"Some friends make fun of me. This makes me feel very embarrassed and anxious when I speak." (Ö2)

“The classroom is very noisy, and some friends are always talking. I get distracted. This makes me lose my focus, and my anxiety increases when I do not know what to do. When it is my turn to speak, I get even more nervous and afraid I will not be able to say the right thing.” (Ö14)

Table 8. Students' views on the strategies they use to reduce oral expression anxiety

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Strategies used to reduce anxiety	Preparing for a speech	Rehearsing your speech at home	9	31,03
	Using notes	Referencing your notes during the presentation	7	24,14
	Calming down	Deep breathing and relaxing	7	24,14
	Friend assistance	Studying and rehearsing with friends	4	13,79
	Concentrating	Practice in a quiet corner or use concentration techniques	2	6,90

Table 8 presents the strategies students use to reduce anxiety during oral presentations. A total of 29 responses were collected within the scope of the analysis, with students indicating more than one strategy. When examining the distribution of responses, 9 participants (31.03%) reported rehearsing their speech at home, 7 participants (24.14%) used notes during the presentation, 7 participants (24.14%) took deep breaths and relaxed, 4 participants (13.79%) studied and rehearsed with friends, and 2 participants (6.90%) studied in a quiet corner and focused as anxiety-reducing methods.

In this context, to better understand the strategies students adopt to reduce oral presentation anxiety, some participants' opinions are presented below with direct quotes:

“I rehearse my speech at home several times. This way, I feel more comfortable during class.” (Ö5)

“I keep short notes with me during my presentation. I can refer to them if I forget, which gives me confidence.” (Ö14)

“I take deep breaths and calm myself down. This way, my heart beats slower, and my anxiety decreases.” (Ö2)

“I practice presentations with my friends. We listen to each other and give each other suggestions, which reduces my anxiety.” (Ö16)

“It is hard to concentrate in class, so I usually go to an empty corner and work quietly. I feel more comfortable there, and my anxiety during the speech decreases.” (Ö9)

Table 9. Students' views on a learning environment where they can express themselves more easily

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Comfortable expression environment	Supportive teacher	A patient, encouraging, and understanding approach	11	36,67
	Peer support	Helpful and supportive colleagues	8	26,66

Interactive and participatory	Group work and activities	6	20,00
Visuals and tools	Use of presentations and supporting materials	2	6,67
Silence and order	A noise-free and distraction-free environment	2	6,67
Physical order	Comfortable seating and ample space	1	3,33

Table 9 presents students' opinions on a learning environment that allows them to express themselves more freely. A total of 30 opinions were obtained within the scope of the analysis, and students mentioned more than one environmental feature. Looking at the distribution of opinions, 11 students (36.67%) found supportive teacher attitudes important, 8 students (26.66%) peer support, 6 students (20.00%) interactive and participatory activities, 2 students (6.67%) use of learning materials, 2 students (6.67%) silence and order, and 1 student (3.33%) physical organization.

In this context, to gain a deeper understanding of students' opinions about a learning environment where they can express themselves more freely, some participants' statements are presented below with direct quotes:

"If our teacher is more patient and encouraging, I feel less afraid when speaking." (Ö17)

"I feel more comfortable when my friends help me, and we work together or give presentations." (Ö2)

"I find it easier to speak when we do group work and games, and my anxiety decreases." (Ö7)

"If the classroom is quiet and no one disturbs each other, it is easier to speak." (Ö1)

"If my seat is comfortable and spacious in the classroom, I feel more at ease; it is easier to speak during class." (Ö11)

"If we use pictures and slides in our presentations, speaking is easier; I feel more at ease because I do not forget what to say."(Ö18)

Table 10. Solution suggestions to reduce students' oral expression anxiety

Theme	Category	Code	N	%
Suggestions for reducing oral expression anxiety	Supportive teacher	A patient, encouraging, and understanding approach	12	22,22
	Rehearsal and planning	Breaking down the speech into sections and rehearsing	8	14,81
	Peer support	Group work and motivating each other	8	14,81
	Preparation and planning	Allowing time before the speech and preparing notes.	7	12,97
	Positive self-talk	Self-motivation and encouragement	5	9,26
	Visuals and tools	Using slides, posters, or drawings	5	9,26
	Calming and breathing techniques	Deep breathing, relaxation, and positive thinking	4	7,41

Focus techniques	Concentrating and avoiding distractions	3	5,56
Quiet and organized classroom	A noise-free and distraction-free environment	1	1,85
Comfortable space and seating	Comfortable seating and use of personal space	1	1,85

Table 10 shows students' suggestions and solutions for reducing oral presentation anxiety. A total of 54 comments were obtained within the scope of the analysis, and students offered more than one solution. Looking at the distribution of comments, the most frequent suggestions (22.22%) were for the teacher's supportive and patient approach. This was followed by rehearsal and planning (14.81%), peer support (14.81%), and preparation/planning (12.97%). Positive self-talk and the use of visuals were each recommended by 9.26%, while calming down and breathing techniques were each recommended by 7.41%, focus techniques by 5.56%, and a quiet, organized classroom environment and comfortable seating by 1.85%.

In this context, to better understand students' solutions and suggestions for reducing oral presentation anxiety, some participants' statements are presented below with direct quotes:

"Teachers should encourage students and avoid scolding them when they make mistakes. This way, students can speak more freely." (Ö15)

"Rehearsals should be done at home before speaking. This method reduces anxiety in class." (Ö3)

"Students should work with their peers and motivate each other. This makes speaking easier." (Ö1)

"Notes should be prepared before speaking, and time should be planned. This gives students confidence." (Ö11)

"Visuals such as pictures and slides should be used during presentations. This can reduce anxiety by preventing students from forgetting what to say." (Ö5)

"Calming techniques such as deep breathing and positive self-talk are beneficial. This helps students stay calm." (Ö13)

"A comfortable desk should be chosen in the classroom, and distractions around it should be reduced". (Ö9)

"It is beneficial to practice in a quiet area before speaking in class. Without noise, you can focus better and will not get as excited while speaking." (Ö7)

4. CONCLUSION

This study examined the sources of anxiety that secondary school students face during oral expression activities in Turkish lessons, along with personal and environmental factors influencing this anxiety, as well as strategies and solutions to reduce it. According to research findings, Turkish teachers reported that students most often experience anxiety related to public speaking or speaking in crowded classrooms, being unable to sustain a conversation when they go to the blackboard, being caught off guard by sudden questions, making mistakes when the teacher expects a specific answer, performing poorly, making mistakes and being ridiculed, being unable to sustain a conversation due to inadequate preparation, and being ridiculed or humiliated

by peers. Student opinions also align with teachers' statements, with middle school students reporting the greatest anxiety about public speaking, responding to teacher questions, fear of making mistakes, presenting on the smartboard, and facing peer reactions. This suggests that student performance declines under social pressure. A review of related literature reveals studies that support these findings. The most prominent cause of speech anxiety is the fear of public speaking. This aligns with Breakey's (2005) statement that approximately 14% of societies experience speech anxiety, and that in many individuals, this anxiety becomes a phobia. Similarly, Ayres and Hopf (1993) highlighted that individuals with a fear of public speaking often avoid such situations. Moreover, as Muallimoğlu (2021) pointed out, many famous figures, including Daniel Webster, John Bright, Abraham Lincoln, and Winston Churchill, experienced a fear of public speaking at different points in their lives. These examples show that speaking anxiety is not limited to students but is a universal phenomenon that can be observed even in experienced individuals.

According to research findings, Turkish teachers identified personal factors that influence the emergence of oral expression anxiety in middle school students as lack of self-confidence, level of preparation, and students' individual characteristics. Teachers also mentioned environmental factors like peer pressure and anxiety about criticism, classroom atmosphere, and teacher attitudes. Student opinions support these findings, with students stating that factors such as lack of self-confidence, lack of preparation, peer relationships, teacher attitudes, and classroom environment are key reasons for oral expression anxiety. This shows that both students' personal perceptions of efficacy and environmental factors affect anxiety. The findings also show that lack of self-confidence and lack of preparation are major contributors to speaking anxiety. This aligns with Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, as students' lack of self-efficacy increases anxiety during speaking. Regarding environmental factors, teachers' critical or harsh attitudes seem to raise student anxiety. For instance, Nepali's (2022) study found that strict and error-focused teacher attitudes significantly heightened students' speaking anxiety. Furthermore, Fadillah et al. (2024) indicated that teachers' classroom attitudes are crucial in reducing students' speaking anxiety. These findings support other research showing that teacher support and positive feedback improve students' speaking performance. Özcanlı and Kozikoğlu (2023) discovered that middle school students experience English-speaking anxiety due to lack of self-confidence, a hostile classroom atmosphere, personality traits, and frequent teacher intervention. They also found that students felt inadequate when speaking English, feared making mistakes, were shy around peers, and worried about their teachers. The results align with existing research findings. Turkish teachers suggested that to reduce middle school students' oral expression anxiety, they provide one-on-one support, establish reassuring communication, implement activities to build self-confidence, inform students beforehand, gradually introduce practice, and foster a positive classroom climate. Students highlighted that the most common strategies to decrease anxiety include practicing speeches, using notes, employing breathing and calming techniques, working with peers, and engaging in concentration activities. Özcanlı and Kozikoğlu (2023) also found that students feel more comfortable speaking when they are not mocked for mistakes or afraid of making them. They emphasized that continuous speaking activities, reinforcement, and indirect error correction are essential. They concluded that students feel more at ease when they have self-confidence, receive teacher support, talk with close friends, and are not mocked by peers. Özdemir (2018), in research with Turkish teacher candidates, found that prepared speeches help reduce speaking anxiety. The results of these studies are consistent with the findings of the relevant research.

Turkish teachers indicated that they exhibit a supportive attitude, aim to foster a trusting classroom climate, practice conscious and respectful listening, include student-centered activities, create an attentive listening environment, and effectively utilize technological tools to help students express themselves more openly. Conversely, students described environments where they could express themselves more freely as involving a supportive teacher attitude, peer support, interactive and participatory activities, a quiet and orderly classroom setting, the use of visuals, and physical comfort. Another important finding of the study was that students reported reducing their anxiety through peer support and participatory activities. This confirms previous research showing that supportive learning environments help students relax during speaking and improve communication skills. For example, a study with Chinese undergraduate students found that peer support increased self-efficacy and reduced foreign-language speaking anxiety (Huang, 2023). Additionally, other experimental studies in collaborative learning settings have shown that group activities significantly lower students' speaking anxiety (Amini & Bicen, 2024). In this context, the results of this middle school study indicate that student interaction and social support play an important role in reducing speaking anxiety. Moreover, students' mention of strategies such as breathing exercises, positive self-talk, using visuals, and maintaining classroom order shows that managing anxiety involves pedagogical, psychological, and physical elements. Therefore, teachers' roles in providing emotional support and organizing the learning environment should be considered together when developing speaking skills.

According to research findings, Turkish teachers reported using various strategies to reduce students' speaking anxiety, including small steps and gradual process management, practices aimed at improving speaking skills, providing reinforcement and support, teacher guidance, exposure and repetition activities, confidence-building activities, distraction techniques, and non-testing and individualized practice. Students mentioned that teachers should adopt a more patient, understanding, and encouraging attitude to help reduce anxiety. They also suggested that practices such as regular rehearsal, planning, positive thinking, using visual materials, and maintaining proper classroom organization can effectively decrease speaking anxiety. In their research, Özcanlı and Kozikoğlu (2023) found that a classroom atmosphere of mutual respect is essential for reducing students' speaking anxiety, and that students should be motivated and confident. They noted that making mistakes is a natural part of the language learning process, and that teaching techniques that are fun and engaging should be employed. Additionally, teachers should aim to be role models. However, they also emphasized that students should be motivated by teachers without constant intervention, a positive classroom atmosphere should be cultivated, and speaking activities should take place only after students have acquired sufficient vocabulary and grammar knowledge of the topic. Aydın (2013) highlighted that the teacher's role significantly influences students' success in speaking education. He stated that teachers should guide children and serve as role models to support their development in multiple aspects. A study by Sevy-Biloon (2017) found that play-centered language teaching practices facilitate students' internalization and use of both grammar and vocabulary. Demir and Özdil (2019) argued that a lack of activities and insufficient emphasis on speaking skills hinder students from achieving adequate mastery of speaking. They also mentioned that activities like reading literary texts aloud and practicing tongue twisters can help improve speaking skills. Maden et al. (2011) asserted that student-centered activities and strategies can help students build self-confidence, develop thinking skills, and express their thoughts more effectively.

The findings of this study show that students' anxiety during oral expression in Turkish language classes is complex and affected by both personal and environmental factors. Based on

the data, the following strategies and recommendations are offered to help reduce students' anxiety levels and enhance their oral expression skills:

- Teachers should adopt a patient, understanding, and encouraging approach to lessen students' anxiety during oral presentations.
- Providing positive feedback is essential to counteract the negative effects of critical and error-focused attitudes.
- Students should be encouraged to rehearse, break down their speech into parts, and prepare brief notes before speaking or presenting.
- Preparation should be carried out systematically with teacher guidance and planning support.
- Classroom activities should be interactive, including group work, game-based learning, and paired presentations.
- The classroom environment should be quiet, organized, and free of distractions to help students focus.
- Seating arrangements should be designed to ensure students feel comfortable both physically and psychologically.
- Visual and supporting materials (slides, posters, pictures, etc.) should be encouraged in presentations and oral activities.
- Students should be aware that oral presentation anxiety is normal and that strategies exist to manage it.
- Oral expression activities should be introduced gradually and regularly, increasing in frequency as students improve their anxiety management skills.

Etik Kurul İzni: Araştırma makaleleri için makale başvurusunda dergi sistemine yüklenen "Etik Kurul Onay Belgesi"ne ilişkin "kurum adı, tarih, sayı vb." bilgiler burada verilir. (Makale yayına kabul edildikten sonra eklenir). Veya çalışma konusu etik kurul iznini gerektirmemektedir.

Katkı Oranı: Yazarlar çalışmaya eşit oranda katkıda bulunmuştur.

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GENİŞLETİLMİŞ ÖZET

GİRİŞ

Konuşma kaygısı yalnızca duygusal bir sorun değil, aynı zamanda öğrenme sürecini doğrudan etkileyen bir öz-yeterlik meselesidir. Bandura'nın (1997) öz-yeterlik kuramına göre, bireyin bir görevi başarıyla yerine getirebileceğine dair inancı, performansını belirleyen en güçlü psikolojik değişkendir. Öz-yeterliği yüksek öğrenciler, zorlayıcı görevlerde bile çaba göstermeye devam ederken öz-yeterliği düşük olanlar başarısızlık beklentisiyle kaçınma eğilimi göstermektedir (Pajares ve Schunk, 2001). Arslan (2018) ve Arslan vd. (2019) tarafından yapılan araştırmalar, öğrencilerin akademik öz-yeterlik düzeyleri arttıkça konuşma kaygılarının anlamlı biçimde azaldığını göstermiştir. Benzer şekilde, Zhang vd. (2020) de öğrencilerin öz-yeterlik düzeyinin konuşma performansına doğrudan katkı sağladığını bildirmiştir.

Türkiye'de konuşma kaygısı üzerine yapılan çok sayıda çalışma mevcuttur (Sallabaş, 2012; Kavruk ve Deniz, 2015; Şen ve Boylu, 2015; Arslan, 2018; Akalın ve Adıgüzel, 2020; Aydın ve Kayman, 2021; Keşaplı ve Çifci, 2024). Ayrıca alan yazınında, ortaokul öğrencilerinin konuşma becerilerinin öğretmen görüşlerine göre değerlendirildiği (Demir ve Gül-Özdil, 2019), Türkçe öğretmeni adaylarının konuşma kaygısını gidermede hazırlıklı konuşmanın etkisinin incelendiği (Özdemir, 2018), sınıf öğretmenliği öğrencilerinin konuşma kaygı düzeylerinin araştırıldığı (Kuru, 2018), sözlü anlatım dersinde yapılan uygulamaların öğretmen adaylarının konuşma kaygıları üzerindeki etkisinin incelendiği (Kuşdemir ve Katrancı, 2015), ortaokul öğrencilerinin İngilizce konuşma kaygılarının öğretmen ve öğrenci görüşlerine göre değerlendirildiği (Özcanlı ve Kozikoğlu, 2023) çeşitli çalışmalara rastlanmıştır. Buna karşın, özellikle Türkçe derslerinde öğrencilerin yaşadıkları sözlü anlatım kaygısını hem öğrencilerin kendi görüş ve deneyimlerine hem de bu süreçte tanıklık eden öğretmenlerin değerlendirmelerine dayalı olarak inceleyen çalışmaların sınırlı olduğu dikkati çekmektedir. Oysa sözlü anlatım becerileri, öğrencilerin düşüncelerini yapılandırma, duygularını aktarmaları ve sosyal etkileşimlerde etkin rol almaları açısından kritik bir öneme sahiptir. Bu doğrultuda, mevcut literatürdeki söz konusu boşluğu doldurmayı amaçlayan bu araştırma, ortaokul öğrencilerinin Türkçe derslerinde yaşadıkları sözlü anlatım kaygısının temel kaynaklarını öğretmen ve öğrenci görüşleri doğrultusunda sistematik bir biçimde ortaya koymayı ve bu kaygıyı azaltmaya yönelik öğrenci merkezli ve öğretmen destekli çözüm önerileri geliştirmeyi hedeflemektedir. Araştırmanın bulgularının, öğretim süreçlerinin tasarlanması ve eğitim politikalarının geliştirilmesi açısından hem akademik hem de uygulamalı düzeyde katkılar sağlaması beklenmektedir.

Bu araştırmanın amacı, ortaokul öğrencilerinin Türkçe derslerindeki sözlü anlatım etkinlikleri sırasında yaşadıkları kaygının nedenlerini ortaya koymak ve bu kaygıyı azaltmaya yönelik çözüm yollarını öğrencilerin ve Türkçe öğretmenlerinin bakış açısından değerlendirmektir.

YÖNTEM

Bu araştırma, nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden durum çalışması deseni kullanılarak yürütülmüştür. Durum çalışması, belirli bir olgunun kendi gerçek yaşam bağlamı içinde derinlemesine incelenmesini amaçlayan bir nitel araştırma desenidir (Yin, 2018). Bu yaklaşım, araştırmacının "ne", "nasıl" ve "neden" sorularına bütüncül biçimde yanıt aramasına olanak sağlar.

Bu araştırma, 2025-2026 eğitim-öğretim yılının birinci döneminde Van ilindeki bir devlet ortaokulunda öğrenim gören 5, 6, 7 ve 8. sınıf öğrencileriyle yürütülmüştür. Araştırmanın çalışma grubunu toplam 18 öğrenci oluşturmaktadır. Katılımcılar, araştırmaya gönüllü olarak katılmayı kabul eden öğrenciler arasından seçilmiştir. Çalışma grubunda 10 kız ve 8 erkek öğrenci yer

almakta olup farklı sınıf düzeylerinden öğrencilerin dâhil edilmesi, sözlü anlatım kaygısının sınıf düzeyine göre değişimlerini gözleme imkânı sağlamıştır.

Ayrıca araştırmacının çalışma grubunda aynı ildeki dört farklı ortaokulda görev yapan toplam 14 Türkçe öğretmeni de yer almaktadır. Öğretmenlerin 8'i kadın, 6'sı ise erkektir. Öğrencilerle birlikte öğretmenlerin de çalışmaya dâhil edilmesi, sözlü anlatım kaygısının hem öğrenci deneyimleri hem de öğretmen gözlemleri açısından çok yönlü olarak incelenmesine olanak sağlamıştır.

Veri Toplama Aracı

Veriler, araştırmacılar tarafından geliştirilen yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formu aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Görüşme formu hazırlanırken literatürdeki konuşma kaygısı ve öz-yeterlik temelli çalışmalardan yararlanılmıştır.

Veri Toplama Süreci

Görüşmeler, öğrencilerin yazılı izinleri alınarak gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırma kapsamında, okul ortamında öğrencilerin dikkatlerinin dağılmayacağı ve rahat bir şekilde formu doldurabilecekleri sessiz bir ortam sağlanmıştır. Her bir öğrenci yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formunu kendisi doldurmuştur. Formu doldurma süresi, öğrenciden öğrenciye değişmekle birlikte ortalama 25 dakika sürmüştür.

Araştırmacılar, öğrencilerin soruları doğru anlayabilmeleri ve gerektiğinde yönlendirici açıklamalar alabilmeleri için süreç boyunca yanlarında bulunmuştur. Formların doldurulmasının ardından yanıtlar titizlikle toplanmış ve analiz için hazır hâle getirilmiştir. Bu yöntem, öğrencilerin düşüncelerini kendi ifadeleriyle aktarmalarını sağlamış ve verilerin güvenilir şekilde toplanmasına olanak tanımıştır.

Öğretmenlerden veri toplama süreci de benzer şekilde yürütülmüştür. Öğretmen görüşmeleri için okul idaresi ve öğretmenlerden gerekli izinler alınmış, öğretmenlerin ders programlarına uygun olarak sessiz ve uygun bir ortam oluşturulmuştur. Öğretmenler, kendileri için hazırlanan yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formunu bireysel olarak doldurmuşlardır. Formun tamamlanma süresi ortalama 20-30 dakika arasında değişmiştir. Süreç boyunca araştırmacılar, soruların açıklığa kavuşturulması gereken durumlarda öğretmenlere gerekli bilgilendirmeleri yapmıştır. Öğretmen formlarından elde edilen yanıtlar da aynı titizlikle toplanarak analiz sürecine dâhil edilmiştir. Bu uygulama, öğretmenlerin gözlem ve deneyimlerini ayrıntılı biçimde ifade etmelerine imkân tanımış ve verilerin çok yönlü bir şekilde toplanmasına katkı sağlamıştır.

Verilerin Analizi

Araştırmadan elde edilen veriler, nitel araştırmalarda yaygın olarak kullanılan içerik analizi yöntemiyle çözümlenmiştir. Bu yöntemle, öğretmenlerin ve öğrencilerin yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formlarına verdikleri yanıtlar dikkatlice incelenmiş ve anlamlı birimlere ayrıştırılmıştır. Öğretmen ve öğrenci ifadeleri, temel anlam birimleri olarak kodlanmış, benzer içerik ve anlam taşıyan kodlar bir araya getirilerek kategorilere dönüştürülmüş ve nihayetinde daha geniş temalar hâline getirilmiştir.

SONUÇ

Araştırma bulgularına göre Türkçe öğretmenleri, öğrencilerin en çok topluluk önünde konuşma ya da kalabalık sınıf ortamında söz alma, tahtaya çıktıklarında konuşmayı sürdürmemeye, ani sorulara hazırlıksız yakalanma, öğretmenin belirli bir yanıt beklediği durumlarda hata yapma, performans sergileme, yanlış söyleyip komik duruma düşme, yetersiz hazırlık nedeniyle konuşmayı sürdürmemeye ve arkadaşları tarafından alay edilme veya küçük düşürülme gibi kaygılar yaşadıklarını belirtmişlerdir. Öğrenci görüşleri de öğretmenlerin ifadeleriyle örtüşmekte olup ortaokul öğrencileri en çok topluluk önünde konuşma, öğretmen tarafından yöneltilen sorulara yanıt verme, yanlış yapma korkusu, akıllı tahtada sunum yapma ve akran tepkileriyle karşı karşıya kalma durumlarında kaygı yaşadıklarını ifade etmişlerdir. Bu

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durum, öğrencilerin performanslarının sosyal değerlendirme baskısı altında azaldığını göstermektedir.